

Children's literature, mathematics education and diversity

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This article aims to investigate the potential of connecting mathematics, children's literature, and ethnic-racial issues in the early years of elementary school. Based on qualitative methodology, the data were produced in a group of 1st-graders of a public school in Brazil and registered through videos, photos, and notes in the field diary. We analysed a didactic sequence developed over three days, working with magnitudes and measures based on the book Mama Panya's Pancakes: A Village Tale from Kenya. The results indicate that students participated more when the mathematical concept was introduced through a children's literature story. The protagonism of the black characters, inserted in a positive context in the story, contributed to constructing a positive cultural identity, leading children to appreciate cultural diversity.

Introduction

The book *Reading and writing the world with mathematics: toward a pedagogy for social justice* (Gutstein, 2006) emphasizes the importance of the political and social dimensions of the teaching of mathematics. Inspired by Freire (2014), the author emphasizes that mathematics education can also contribute for students to read the world and actively participate in the transformation of situations of oppression. Among the goals of mathematics education for social justice is the development of cultural positive and social identities (Gutstein, 2006). In the author's words, "by positive cultural identities, I mean that students are strongly rooted in their home languages, cultures, and communities, but at the same time, can appropriate what they need to survive and thrive in the dominant culture" (Gutstein, 2006, p. 28). In this sense, a critical educator should support the development of positive cultural identities through actions in the classroom that values the students' background, language, and culture, developing a pedagogy in which these aspects are contemplated, becoming a source for learning (Gutstein, 2006). In other words, a culturally relevant pedagogy (Ladson-Billings, 1994).

Gutstein (2006) developed his conception of mathematics education for social justice by working mainly with adolescents rather than with young children. However, his in-depth analysis of mathematics education for social justice inspires thinking about mathematical

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literacy. What does it mean to develop positive cultural identities when the mathematics teaching and learning process has children from the early years of elementary school as participants? Seeking to discuss possibilities inspired by this perspective, we will explore some potentialities of children's literature linked to mathematics and racial issues.

Children's literature and mathematics

Several mathematical educators (Montoito, 2019; Souza, Carneiro, 2015) have highlighted the importance of literature and children's literature in mathematics classes. According to Souza and Carneiro (2015, p. 393), "children's literature encompasses the so-called "classic" literature books and texts, such as the Brothers Grimm's stories and Andersen's tales, among others; contemporary texts, also called "realistic tales," and aimed at children, and paradidactic books."¹ Souza and Carneiro (2015) also point out that paradidactic books are developed to teach didactic content using literature playfully, with illustrative characters in real and hypothetical contexts, enabling dialogue through textual elements such as setting, characters, and conflicts.

Teaching mathematics connected to children's literature enables a pleasant approximation between children and mathematics, provides a context for mathematical terms, besides being based on the commitment of all disciplines to the children's literacy process. Montoito (2019) emphasises that all disciplines are committed to students' literacy, mathematics included. The author also points out how important it is to put on mathematical glasses when reading a story to analyse what it can represent in aspects different from merely literary ones, paying attention to the story's potential rather than the plot. This is the first step to start seeing literature from other aspects, as a literary tale can bring several teaching possibilities. Therefore, all teachers should encourage reading, regardless of the subject they teach. This posture is crucial for the development of a good reader. This perspective is productive not only for students but also for the teacher, who can help students develop creativity, can explore their imaginary and symbolic potentials.

In this way, mathematics classrooms have become a meeting place for children, characters, and mathematical concepts through the books *Problems of the Gorgonzola Family*² (Furnari, 2004), *The Duck Lollipop*³ (Machado, 2003), *Who's Going to Keep the Peach?*⁴ (Ah-Hae; Hyewon, 2010). Fairy tales, also offer rich situations for the elaboration of mathematical problems and investigative situations. However, looking at the mathematics classroom and children's literature, inspired by the perspective of mathematics education for social justice, means being concerned with developing positive cultural identities for children and going

¹ "a literatura infantil engloba os livros e os textos ditos "clássicos" da literatura, como as histórias dos irmãos Grimm e os contos de Andersen, entre outros; os textos contemporâneos, também denominados "contos realistas" e direcionados ao público infantil; e os livros paradidáticos" (Souza; Carneiro, 2015, p. 393).

² Os problemas da Família Gorgonzola (Furnari, 2004).

³ O Pirulito do Pato (Machado, 2003).

⁴ Quem vai ficar com o pêssego? (Ah-Hae; Hyewon, 2010).

beyond the “Once Upon a Time,” in which most characters have a stereotyped beauty for example, linked to characteristics of white phenotypes and European culture.

Children’s literature books have verbal and non-verbal elements that are not neutral and can contribute to constructing a positive cultural identity for children but can also make them disregard their culture and background. Therefore, it is essential that teachers connect children’s literature, mathematics, and the positive representation of black characters from the beginning of schooling. Therefore, a set of essential questions emerged: What children’s literature book should we take to the classroom? What does a book offer so that students enjoy it? How are the characters in this book? What are the settings? Will this book help children travel to other places? Does it bring the diversity and richness of different cultures and contribute to constructing a positive cultural identity? Does it contribute to mathematics being worked in an interdisciplinary way and potentiates the triggering of problem situations?

It is essential that books such as *Bia na África* (Dreguer, 2016), *Handa’s Surprise* (Browne, 2001), *Mama Panya’s Pancakes: A Village Tale from Kenya* (Chamberlin & Chamberlin, 2005), *The Color of Coraline* (Rampazo, 2017) and *The Little Black Prince* (França, 2020), whose characters are black children in positive contexts, also enter mathematics classes. In this way, this article aims to investigate the potential of connecting mathematics, children’s literature, and ethnic-racial issues in the early years of elementary school.

Methodology

The development of this work was supported by a qualitative approach (Bogdan & Biklen, 1994) and used participant observation. This study was conducted in a class of 1st-graders of elementary school of a state public school in a city in the countryside of Mato Grosso do Sul (MS). The group was composed of 31 students and the teacher. The activities analyzed in this paper were developed in this class by the first author, as part of the activities of the Institutional Program for Teaching Initiation Scholarships (PIBID)⁵, of the UFMS/CPNV subproject, coordinated by the second author.

The activities were developed in three meetings, held on Tuesdays, preceded by the subproject meetings at UFMS/CPNV, which aimed to deepen the theoretical knowledge about mathematical literacy and develop didactic sequences based on the discussions. The data were registered through videos, photos, and notes in the field diary, which we analysed later. We watched the video recordings several times to delve into the data and made notes to help describe the context. We also identified events that contributed to understanding the research object and confirming or refuting our hypotheses. Among those events, there were some of the students’ speeches, which we transcribed, developing the episodes.

This article addresses a didactic sequence to work on mathematics along with children’s literature and ethnic-racial issues. The didactic sequence is described in three episodes and analysed from its contributions to the teaching and learning of the mathematical concepts, appreciation of diversity and the fight against racism.

⁵ Programa Institucional de Bolsas de Iniciação à Docência (PIBID).

A history in Kenya: Possibilities in mathematics classes

At the beginning of the class, it was agreed that students could participate and ask by raising their hands so that everyone could hear their arguments or their questions. With the support of a projector, we began a journey with them based on the story *Mama Panya's Pancakes: A Tale from a Village in Kenya* by Mary and Rich Chamberlin (Figure 1). It is about Mama Panya and a boy named Adika, who walk to a street market to buy ingredients for pancakes. On the way, the boy meets several friends and invites them all to eat pancakes at his home. During the development of the plot, the story also covers several aspects of Kenya and the African continent.

Figure 1: Book cover

Silence filled the classroom. The students were delighted and attentive. At the end of the story, we began the discussion by asking them whether they had noticed anything different in the history of that country. Some observed Adika and Mama Panya's clothes, while one student spontaneously and curiously exclaimed: "Wow, how well they dress, the clothes are so beautiful and colourful!" Others commented that the market was different from the ones they knew. They highlighted the characteristics of the animals, the trees, and the school. In the final pages of the book, there is information about the school, the village, and the animals. One student mentions the long distance between school and homes. After that, we started talking about the routes they had to take from their homes to school, describing it as long or short.

Some students said they lived very close; others emphasised that they lived far. To understand better the routes they had to take, they drew a picture. While they were drawing the routes, a student asked: "Teacher, do I need to draw the curves I make when I turn around a corner?" Seizing the moment, another sketched another question: "Do I need to draw the houses I see on the way home?" We replied that they could draw the way they thought the

best and bring details like houses, markets, and corners when they took other directions. Realising the students' doubts, we went from table to table, solving questions and discussing ideas of specific points, among other details that emerged during the drawings. Then, a dialogue was opened on the importance of using terms such as right, left, starting point, and it was collectively established that the starting point would be the school gate.

After finishing the drawing, each student shared their route with the rest of the class, explaining it orally. The first student found it a little challenging. We told them that they could walk around the room, showing the route. The students understood it. Some got up and walked around the room as they had described. Others explained their spatial location orally, without getting up. Subsequently, we read the recipe that Mama Panya used in the story and brought a text with curiosities about the origin of pancakes and how different they can be from country to country. Besides mathematics, we addressed the identification of textual genres. The students were encouraged to notice the difference between a recipe and other textual genres. For example, when asked if they knew how to identify a recipe, a student shared her answer with the class: "You can see it because the recipe the teacher gave is smaller and has numbers, and I don't see it in the other texts." Therefore, all learned the structure of a recipe: ingredients, preparation method, how to serve, and how many people it serves. Subsequently, we commented on the fractional numbers present in the recipe. Some students explained that these numbers represented divisions; others could not answer.

A cup, spoons, packages of wheat flour, and containers were brought into the classroom and used to contextualise the fractional numbers in the recipe. After that, the students read the recipe on the board and identified the mixed number referring to the measure to be placed, taking the amount in a cup straight from the wheat flour package and placing it in the container.

As some students did not understand the fractional part of the number, one child was willing to explain. Going to the front of the class, she read the recipe on the blackboard and said, "This recipe says to put two cups, you will take the cup and fill it twice and put the filling in the bowl. In front of the number two, there is another number, $\frac{1}{2}$, which is the same as for the chocolate. You have a bar of chocolate with two pieces, don't you? If I eat one piece, how many are left?" The rest of the class replied that it was one. Next, she said, "Yes, but as the chocolate was composed of two pieces and I ate one, there was one piece left, which was half! We know it represents half; then, you will put half a cup more," showing everyone in the class with the wheat and the cup. After this explanation, no questions remained, and the students took turns to participate with different measures until everyone understood it. With this, the class was finished.

Pancakes

There were thirty students in class at the second meeting, which we began by asking if the students remembered the story read in the previous class. They explained some characteristics of the book *Mama Panya's Pancakes* orally. They mentioned the market, how

the characters dressed and spoke, the trees, the animals, the school, and the distance the characters had to walk to get there.

Then, we asked whether they remembered what Mama Panya was planning to cook when she decided she was going to the market to buy ingredients, to which they all replied very enthusiastically that it was the pancakes. Next, the conversation was about pancakes around the world, how each culture had its way and adaptations to prepare them: some usually use meat, ham, and mozzarella; others make them sweet, with chocolate, with condensed milk, and even only the dough with pepper, just like Mama Panya's. Then, we discussed who had already eaten pancakes and how they had been prepared. Everyone got involved and told how families used to prepare them. "Mine [referring to the cook] puts on minced meat, and we eat them for lunch," one student exclaimed. "Mine puts cheese on top and bakes in the oven!" stated another, and some reported that they had never tasted it.

Thus, a pancake recipe was written on the board to be prepared in the classroom. We organised some space, placing a table in front with all the ingredients to analyse the instructions and measure. We asked the class to read the whole recipe aloud so that they could get used to the structure of the genre. Then, students came in pairs to prepare the food. However, it was not that simple; they had to get into the mood of chefs de cuisine. To characterise the moment of preparing recipes, the students put on caps and aprons. One of them joked, "Now we're mini master chefs." The recipe was made step by step: each one went to the front, put on a cap, an apron and read out loud the ingredient to be added and its quantity, placing it in the container as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Student adding milk.

After finishing adding all the ingredients, the next in line placed the mixture in another container. Then, they read the recipe, analysing what should be done next. The students pointed out that the recipe is for six servings and that this would not be enough for everyone.

They calculated how many times it would be necessary to repeat the recipe for the 30 students to eat. After talking to each other, they solved the issue together on the board.

The recipe was duplicated by adding six and six, and the teacher took notes on the board, and the students said: “12”. Then, we analysed: “Is a recipe for twelve people the ideal?” They said: no. It would be necessary to add one more. The teacher wrote on the board: $12+6$, and some students answered “18!” They were asked, “Is it fine now? Will all be served?” And they said: no, it would be necessary to add some more. Then, the teacher wrote: $18+6$, and they replied, after thinking for a few minutes: “24!” “And now, is everything all right?” asked the teacher. And they answered: no, because there would be not enough for everybody. In this way, another addition was written on the board: $24+6$. This sum was not calculated mentally as the previous ones. To solve it, the students used their notebooks and soon answered that the result was 30 and that now it was right, that it would be enough for all students. At this point, one of the students suggested that one more recipe be made so that the teachers could also taste it and, whatever was left, they would share with everyone else. Thus, it was done.

In this process, the students asked a question: “How many times have we repeated the number six in our calculations?” It was easier to conclude, as the sum was exposed on the board, and the students soon replied loud and clear: “Six times”. They were asked if they all knew what it meant, and a student replied, “That means how many times we’re going to repeat the recipe.” The recipe was repeated six times, giving everyone the opportunity to execute a part of it. Finally, all the dough was placed in a larger container. The students then agreed that the last step, to cook the dough, should be carried out by an adult for safety reasons, so the pancakes were prepared by the first author and the class teacher, and all students tasted them. After that, teachers and students talked about the importance of mathematics for the recipe to end up perfect and the pancakes tasty.

Butterflies

In the third meeting of the discussion on the book *Mama Panya’s Pancakes*, 30 students were present. We began a dialogue on animals, diversity, and richness of the fauna of each country. They were asked if they remembered the animals they had seen in the story. All answered they did and cited some: the giraffe, the zebra, and the tiger. Then again, they were asked, “And the butterfly, does anyone remember?” Students began answering all at once. When they calmed down, we all agreed that everyone could speak, one at a time. They characterised the butterfly as big and beautiful, according to the words of the class. During the discussion, we asked them to give the main characteristic of the Kenyan butterfly.

The class went silent, so we brought up the moment when the story reports the characteristics of the butterfly. Some students started shouting, “Teacher, the Kenyan butterfly is giant.” Then, we looked for the measure of the butterfly in the text, and the students identified that it measured 20 cm from one wing edge to the other. The children sat in pairs, and each received two pieces of string, one measuring 20 cm and the other 7 cm. First, they were asked to analyse the strings and say which one they thought represented the

butterfly from Kenya and which one represented the butterfly from Brazil. They immediately noticed the difference and, to be sure, they all took the rulers. In pairs, they measured the strings to find out the exact size of each one of them. We told them that to use the ruler, they had to start counting from the number "0" onwards, and so they did. After they finished measuring, they chose two children to register the measure of the strings on the board.

Finally, they drew a 20 cm straight line in the notebook with the ruler and drew a butterfly underneath, following the rule that consisted of starting one wing on one end of the line and the other wing on the other end. The students draw beautiful Kenyan butterflies in their notebooks. With the colourful wings of beautiful butterflies on a paper page, the class was finished.

Data analysis

This study shows the potential of working on mathematics along with children's literature and ethnic-racial issues in the first years of elementary school. This connection enables students to learn mathematical knowledge such as quantities and measures addressed in the research while expanding their knowledge of ethnic-racial aspects. Students broadened their knowledge of magnitudes and measures in context, for example, the measures with natural numbers and the introduction to fractional numbers through the recipe brought from a children's literature book. Those numbers had a referent in the story, which helped children to understand them and identify that reference. The preparation of the recipe in the classroom allowed them to handle the ingredients and containers, reflecting on the measures specified in the instructional text and the relation to the equivalent amount of ingredients they should add.

The students also talked about displacement and reference points, reflecting on Adika and Mama Panya's route to the marketplace and described the routes they used to take to go from school to home. The students expanded their vocabulary during the descriptions and started to incorporate words such as turning right, turning left, near and far, and selected reference points they could use. We could show the children how to measure with a ruler from baseline, not using the space before the zero. This activity was developed in the context of the fauna of Kenya, represented by its butterflies, which favoured the children's engagement. At this moment, we also approached the concept of difference between measures by using the strings.

As for ethnic-racial issues, among all aspects, the study emphasised black characters in children's literature in the mathematical literacy process, which plays an extremely relevant role in bringing positive perspectives on black people to the classroom. According to Munanga (2005), the discourses about blacks throughout history, from a western and ethnocentric perspective, presented wild, poor, and inferior peoples, devoid of knowledge, history, and culture. Thus, ethnic-racial relations must be discussed from the beginning of schooling to change this stereotypical view. Educators and authorities must be committed to the educational, cultural, and political fields to present and discuss other approaches on the black population. To this end, Munanga (2005, p. 16) points out that:

The rescue of collective memory and the history of the black community is not only of interest to students of black descent. It is also interesting to students of other ethnic backgrounds, especially white students, because upon receiving an education poisoned by prejudices, they also had their psychic structures affected.

Given this statement, regarding the learning provided on ethnic-racial issues, students could know a little about Kenya and learn that it is a country in the African continent, which allowed them to distance themselves from the Western ethnocentric gaze and recognise the importance of cultural diversity. Students also used positive adjectives to refer to the characters, for example, when they observed Adika and Mama Panya's clothes, and one student spontaneously and curiously argued: "Wow, how well they dress, the clothes are so beautiful and colourful!" According to Pereira and Dias (2020, p. 193), "[...] children deserve a literature that contemplates the multiplicity of stories and lives, recognising the various identities and valuing those that have long been disregarded."

Through this immersion in Kenya, they could value a visit to Africa and its riches without leaving the classroom, as Mary and Rich Chamberlin brought a piece of the country to them. Students were able to create meanings for a children's literature book that brings the representativeness of black characters in a positive context, contributing to the children's development of a positive cultural and social identity (Gutstein, 2006).

Considerations

Throughout this article, we emphasised the potential of combining mathematics, children's literature and ethnic-racial issues in the teaching and learning process, showing that the student-reader can build mathematical knowledge when it is worked in an interdisciplinary, playful, and contextualised way. Among the concepts approached, we highlight: units of measure involving natural and fractional numbers, displacements and spatial notions, use of the ruler to measure, and the concept of difference. Data analysis also allowed us to consider that education is a crucial tool to fight racism. The black characters in stories with positive contexts contribute to the construction of social and cultural identity, the learning and representativeness of the black population, and the construction of a democratic, human, and anti-racist society.

The connection between children's literature, mathematics, and ethnic-racial issues that value the history and culture of the black population is essential for the learning process of all children, regardless of their ethnic-racial belonging. This combination also enabled the teaching and learning of respect for the culture of the other, the identification of diversity and its appreciation, provided to students through the story *Mama Panya's Pancakes: A Tale from a Village in Kenya*.

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